

MARKETING AUTOMATION BY GROWTH HACKING

Mayur Phatak¹, Abhishek Saxena², Psrea Y. Singh³, Soumya Singh⁴

¹Head, Department of IT, Universal Business School, Mumbai, India

^{2, 3, 4}Post Graduate Diploma in Management – 2018-2020, Universal Business School, Mumbai, India

Abstract - Marketing automation is a new-age technology adopted by organizations that automates the entire marketing campaigns, along with the processes, that runs through all the channels. The marketing and the sales department use this to tailor-build campaigns from scratch in order to maximize revenue and amplify the efficiency of work. It ultimately assists the company to expand in size and complexity and saves huge amounts of time and cost for the user as well as the organization. In essence, it streamlines most of the tasks of modern marketing, which would otherwise be time-consuming and simplify its operation, dovetailing into creating a gamut of digital campaigns quickly. It transcends from individual e-mails, messages and content but is a hub for creation that usually uses more than one medium that starts from identifying the right audience, making the right content and communicating on the right channel. Marketing automation drives revenue and Return-On-Investment, while keeping in mind the core functionalities of the business.

Key Words: Marketing Automation, Artificial Intelligence, Live chat, Customer engagement, Mobile applications, Growth hacking etc.

1. INTRODUCTION

Marketing is the livelihood of every B2C relationship. Marketing automation is a the process is automated with a category of software that streamlines and measures the tasks, to maximize revenue and improve operational efficiency, faster. It is also an integral part of customer relationship management. Marketing automation is a software built on purpose, with an application geared on performance.

In the last five years, marketing automation has grown into a \$1.65 billion industry with over 142,000 businesses (including American Express, Intel, LinkedIn) relying on it to run and monitor many of their marketing efforts. With Unica (now known as IBM Omni-channel Marketing) in 1992 to the latest entrants such as HubSpot, WhatsNexx, and Loopfuse, the marketing automation software market is broader and more extensive than ever before, and the average monthly cost of using them has decreased.

Through 2006-2008, with the advent of social media, marketing automation app developers began adding a wide range of tools and capabilities beyond email 2013 saw the most development through acquisitions as Infusionsoft took GroSocial, Marketo took insight era, Adobe grabbed neolane, ExactTarget took pardot, then Salesforce took ExactTarget.

Companies which adopted market automation software for their growth and development sees 451% growth in qualifying leads, 14.5% increase in sales productivity and around 12% reduction in marketing overhead. According to 63% of the surveys conducted the ability to set measurable objectives for each of the campaigns conducted by them is the greatest value of driving the marketing automation.

1.1 Objectives & Hypothesis

- To understand marketing automation.
- To understand features and channels of marketing automation.
- To understand uses of marketing automation in various industries.
- To understand the relation b/w size of the firm and implementation of marketing automation.

1.2 Research Design/ Methodology Plan:

To achieve the part of research study, primary and secondary researches are used to arrive at a conclusive analysis of Marketing Automation, the tomorrows today. The primary research is a result of the interaction and discussion with various heads at Netcore, Mumbai.

The primary study was carried out to understand the expectation of respondents through personal interviews. To achieve full scrutiny on secondary research, some of the leading articles have been referred based on pure discretion, reports published by Pwc, along with data from UNWTO report have been duly studied and conclusion are drawn. To enhance the credibility of the report, some journals have been studied and referred, to understand about marketing automation and draw relevant decisive conclusions. The study was conducted as an exercise of experiential learning which is a peculiar process of learning at UNIVERSAL BUSINESS SCHOOL carried out by the students of Post-Graduate Diploma in Management.

2. Literature Review

The automation industry is the amalgamation of marketing strategies to track the user behaviour data and make a concise decision based on their activities online. It includes the overall process where the companies can gather the user data and then analyse it and find the best channel through

which we can communicate with their customers in the least possible effort with maximum effectiveness.

The user base data, the dashboard, and the other facilities that are provided by the automation services are generally very expensive and cannot be afforded by many such struggling companies which are in genuine need of it.

Growth hack is a very good principle that can actually help companies to retain their growth by the help of the marketing automation services through simple lifetime learnings which can be incorporated by creative methods and ideas such as creating different accounts to access one user database.

To make an effort and have the integration system developed by their own developer to communicate in a better way by the help of the format by itself for marketing automation.

In this research we have gone through different websites of the various marketing automation forms and have tried to understand the approach that they have for their selling of the products the facilities through which it can actually be hacked and move forward.

3. Growth Hacking

Growth hacking means fast experimentation with various marketing strategies, promotional campaigns, web design decisions and other activities to quickly turn leads and generate sales, which is focused on Growth.

Crazy Egg gives tactics for growth hacking, (Crazy Egg, 2019)

I. Collaborative growth through audience sharing

Collaborations are the unsung heroes of the growth hacking, when it comes to visitors. When you have an audience of 50,000 members and another entrepreneur has an audience of 50,000 members in a similar environment, collaborating can work together to reach 100,000 people.

II. Use A/B testing frequently

After running user experience reports like Heatmaps, Scrollmaps, Confetti reports and List reports, Crazy Egg banks heavily on A / B tests on the website. The A / B tests are even more successful when there is data in hand, because we know what to test.

III. Increase presence on relatively small and local events

The goal is to increase local presence to increase growth. If there is a niche-related small events in the vicinity— or even outside the city — consider attending. Meeting people face-to-face, shaking hands and telling them about their needs will make you a more appealing option than an organization without facets.

IV. Drop a bomb in the form of challenge

Creating a competition is a perfect way to build a constructive relationship with your audience and improve your credibility. It may be linked to a personal development purpose, a social cause or a creative initiative. The trick here is to make it something not everyone can do. Here, one is asking people to take up his challenge — not join.

V. E-mail Open Tracker (Smolski, 2019)

One of the simplest advantages of email tracking software is that it provides insights about emails sent. It can provide the operator real-time notifications when an e-mail is opened, this helps in building impactful insights along with apt follow-ups. Additionally, it also automates the whole process and can save many hours/week.

The widely followed example of growth hacking can be,

Live Chat, as of 2015, the number of website visits resulting in live chat sessions has increased considerably, stated by CCW. It is especially popular on low-traffic websites, with about one in seven sessions on sites receiving up to 5,000 visitors a month prompting a live chat conversation. (Patel, 2020)

Online, it is (generally) much harder to get answers to our questions. Of course, we can normally call or send an email, but both approaches have their disadvantages – that is, waiting on hold and long response times for emails.

SuperOffice survey showed that the average organization requires more than 12 hours responding to a customer service complaint, with 62 percent not responding to emails from customer service. In contrast comparison with live chat, which had an average response time of **37 seconds** only. The implementation of conversational marketing has seen leads rise by 30 percent or more each time

Most analytics tools are daunting as they reveal what they have and they say that it is "Big Data." We need analysts to dig up the details, and because of the sampling, they often cannot get it. **Heatmap** comes without sampling and breaks down the Big Data to provide you with the data that makes sense, to monitor your site's output in real time. (Heatmap Inc., 2020)

Live chat systems allow personnel to answer numerous customer queries at once. This increases productivity of the workforce, ensuring you get higher production with fewer employees. Implementing live chat is an activity that cuts cost pertaining to customer service, along with minimizing the number of manpower required to handle customers (answering phones, replying to e-mails).

Live chat has an associated benefit of down-selling that helps in the process of building customers trust towards the brand, and parallel increase in customer engagement, ultimately causing a rise in average value of any order, which in turn can be used to invoke emotions and arouse customer loyalty. (Patel, 2020)

Additionally, live chat is not only restricted troubleshooting-it can have a big effect on your result.

Web chat users are almost three times more likely to switch than those who don't, and 51% of customers are more likely to continue with (or purchase from) a business if it provides live chat help.

Source (Koyako, 2020)

Users like the live chat, really. Customer satisfaction is higher than 80%, with the number of chat sessions between 2016 and 2017 rising by 1.8x.

About, 79% of customers said they prefer to use live chat because they "receive immediate answers to their questions."

Source: (Koyako, 2020)

FEATURES

I. Omni channel Personalization

a. Personalized product recommendation

Algorithms use a wide range of data to produce personalized and most appropriate product suggestions for visitors Most likely to explore, most likely to buy Trending Goods, Review Opportunities, Cross-selling opportunities and Similar Goods Deals to avoid attrition.

b. Personalize across touch points

Properly educated of the most appropriate and personalized items for each user, this technology customizes every consumer touch-point. In a customer journey map there are several touch points that a consumer come across. Automating them will reap fruitful benefits, as we can track the frequency each touch points has.

c. Category page reordering

Typically, every category page has about 150 and 20,000 items everywhere. For each visitor the algorithms will reorder user's complete catalogue showing the most important and customized items on top. Customized catalogues usually have higher conversion rates of 20-30 per cent. Automation enables our customisation algorithms to be seamlessly incorporated with your merchandising rules.

d. Recommendation widgets

All widgets are explicitly designed for the web, utilizing the existing themes. Given the customized and contextual content, higher CTRs and conversions are guaranteed. Whenever visitors are about to leave, the pop-ups automatically activate and instantly guide them in the right direction.

e. Personal Boutique

Thinking of a store which is specially designed for a visitor and customized as per their choice and preferences. Through the online stores, the experience can be rolling out to clients. The personal boutique is a cross-category curation of the items most likely to be purchased or displayed by the consumer, listed in a list format on a single page.

The customer can connect with this page and also press the "Like" "Dislike" buttons to exchange real-time reviews about their preferences and choices.

f. Personalized Ads

Automation, driven by the awareness of the most appropriate items for each user, integrates with Instagram and Google Web to deliver customized ads for each user - Recruit more guests first time, re-engage to get them back

II. Unified Customer View**a. Develop Rich Individual Customer Profiles**

Capture a number of data points for each customer using the mobile app or website. Gain a detailed understanding of customers based on information relevant to their demographic, regional, behavioural, and app. Empower these profiles in real time for your mobile app, website, and marketing strategies focused on every single customer experience.

b. Strengthen your Segmentation Strategy

After more visibility for individual customers, customer segments can be easily generated on the basis of some specified data points. For example, if there is a food delivery app, laser-focused segments can be created based on venue, preferred cuisine, categories of loyalty programs, or payment methods.

c. Send Hyper-Personalized Communication

A consumer 360-degree view enables personalized data-driven multi-channel campaigns to be generated as part of complex marketing automation journeys. The ads that are more personalized; higher customer engagement, conversion, and retention levels. Let consumer data help to improve the efficiency of the campaign.

d. Deliver Consistent Customer

Through defining and monitoring cross-device experiences with the mobile app or website, we get a comprehensive view of the origins and trends of use of the customers. Now offer consistent individualized experiences without having to count twice the same customer. Deepen customer relationships, with one customer engaged at a time.

III. Multichannel Marketing Automation**a. Develop a High-impact Campaign Mix**

One should not limit to one or two communication platforms. Identify which channels work best for stand-alone promotions or automated customer experiences and accordingly good-tune the customer experience approach. And, run all of these data-driven activities on any integrated platform for market automation, easily.

b. Engage Audiences on their Preferred Channels

Embrace user centricity by orchestration of marketing strategies focused on the most active contact platforms and cross-device preferences of your users. Using a combination of AI-powered actionable insights and imaginative independence to guide the combination of channels across each stage of the conversion funnel.

c. Make Automation the Pillar of your Marketing Machinery

Assign additional time and energy to approach while automating the distribution of customized and contextualized communications through platforms and devices based on studied behavioural data and patterns of use. Make better and much more flexible data-driven decisions which fuel development by automating marketing.

IV. Customer Journey Orchestration**a. Make Every Digital Touchpoint Count**

Plan and execute multichannel consumer journeys focused on the priorities of conversion. Automate adaptive workflows that help us communicate with specific consumer segments at the right time, by delivering the right message to the right platform. Turn-off and non-response account for other platforms, and change the journeys on the go.

b. Power Timely Customer Engagement

To deliver rich, contextualized messages, via time accounting, via email, push notifications, in-app messages. Scheduled or time-space crafts and embeds triggered projects throughout your journeys. Also, chart real-time buyer responses to determine the next best step to grow them towards conversion.

c. Hyper-Power Customer Experiences

Mobile app users and visitors to the website would never be following a linear road. React to the slightest shifts in behaviour patterns and isolate consumer segments instantly along the most important route to accelerate conversion via hyper-personalized communication.

d. Leverage Granular Transactional Data

Through collecting deep-dive data based on the activities of your clients, messaging strategies can be further customized by specific suggestions.

V. Contextual App Walkthroughs

a. Deliver Impactful First – Time On boarding Experiences

Exploring and using the app by training them quickly on the registration process, login options, functions of the app, first-time promo codes etc.

b. Handhold and Direct Users Towards Conversion

Render personalized walkthroughs or demos to reach passive users through various on-the-go app screens. Provide these contexts to cause this form of in-app interaction for future users that can be specified to satisfy the eligibility parameters.

c. Highlight New or Underutilised App Features

Get consumers addicted to these features so they gain the full benefit while pushing up the use and retention of repeat devices.

d. Capture Dynamic User Feedback, Real time

Go beyond rankings and reviews to collect live reviews through qualitative surveys from active in-app users. This input will enhance the quality of UIs or products/services.

VI. Actionable App Analytics

a. User Path Analysis

Visualize the most common navigation journeys in the app to feature discovery, transfer, or uninstallation. Zoom in to examine the development of complex user segments between predefined device events and the time between them and their frequency.

b. Rich Qualitative Analysis

Dive deeper into qualitative perspectives on in-app experiences, time spent on each app screen, and live app success at each session at an individual user level.

Truly recognize the user's granular actions to maximize conversion paths and experience on the platform.

c. Uninstall Analysis

Categorize uninstalled users depending on the level they were on when they uninstalled the app in their user journey. Group these users based on their justification for uninstalling spanning factors like efficiency of the app, accessibility and past user behaviour.

d. Retention Analysis

Knowing the key habits of retained users over days, weeks, months and personalized time periods based on retention

metrics. Use these observations to allow new consumer groups to maintain the same or similar in-app behaviour.

VII. Advance Analytics

a. Funnel Analysis

Track specific customer journeys all the way to conversion. Drill-down, break funnels, and pinpoint where they drop off, build consumer segments in real-time, and target them with specific marketing strategies to arrest churn and elevate interaction

b. Cohort Analysis

Compare client groups that display similar behaviours in the mobile app and/or website. Map their actions over custom time periods to evaluate whether each cohort from the time of sign-up/registration stays engaged.

c. Recency Frequency and Monetary Value Analysis

Automated behavioural flywheel segmentation by analysing the Recency, Frequency and Financial Value of transactions made by the customers. Targeting the consumer segments established – ranging from Stars and Loyalists to at Risk and Inactive – with tailored multi-channel strategies supporting marketing investment.

VIII. Artificial Intelligence Marketing

a. Campaign Title Optimisation

Incorporate high-conversion keywords into hyper-personalized subject lines of email or push titles of alerts based on previous experiences with marketing strategies of the clients. It helps to recognize which keywords work better for which segment of consumers, sometimes for the same campaigns.

b. Campaign Content Optimisation

Having every marketing strategy count by refining the content of the message to resonate with the individual clients.

c. Send Time Optimisation

Identify the right time to send your email, push notification or SMS promotions to specific consumer segments when they are most likely accessible and respond to these marketing contacts.

d. Preferred Channel

Based on information derived from historical responses of the customers and experiences with marketing campaigns, it

is possible to determine the channel of communication on which different groups of customers are most involved.

e. Smart Segments

Based on a comprehensive review of behavioural data and predefined consumer segments; new secret and granular segments can be discovered based on past buying, watching, browsing, etc.

CHANNELS

I. App Push Notifications

a. Deliver Hyper-personalised Experiences

Users with highly significant and timely hyper personalised posts. Customize app-based push alerts and personalize them with user profiles such as displayed name, location, time and product.

b. Stand Out with Rich Push Notifications

It simply explains to go beyond to surprise the users with interactive elements such as stickers, emoji, GIFs, videos and audio. The more interactive and customized your posts, the greater the chances of relaunching apps and conversions.

c. Push Through the Noise with Push Amplification

In a crowded app room, making sure the push notification is difficult for every user on all devices. Using the automation to send accelerated push notifications that actually hit your end-user devices and boost delivery speeds by 20%.

d. Boost Your Open Rates with Send Time Optimisation

Using Send Time Optimisation to time the push notification plan to raise open rates. Select the best time to send user responsiveness derived messages. Track user reactions to monitor and correct any changes in user behaviour in real time.

e. Instantly Grab User Attention by Optimizing Push Notifications Subject Lines

Elevate the personalization approach of the program, by refining the subject lines of the push notifications.

In the subject lines Embed suggested high-conversion keywords and emoji focused on sentiment analysis and historical experiences with push notification campaigns of specific user segments.

The more structured and descriptive subject lines, the greater the available rates and conversions for your push notification.

f. Optimize Your App Push Notification Campaigns with A/B and Multivariate Testing.

Send several combinations of copies of texts, creatives, CTAs quickly to an equally distributed audience or to a subset of audiences. Accelerate conversions of the campaigns with A/B checking.

II. Web Push Notifications

a. Turn Your Website Visitors into Customers

b. Engage Your Mobile Web Visitors with Contextual Messages

c. A/B Test Your Notifications for Higher Conversions.

III. In - App Messages

a. Engage with App Users in Real-Time

b. Hyper-personalize in In-App Experience

c. Send Triggered Messages and Broadcasts

d. Measure Campaign Impact and ROI

e. Easily Run Control Groups to Test out Feasibility

IV. Web Messages

a. Trigger Web Message Campaigns Based on Past Customer Behavior

b. Make Micro-Moments Count to Engage in Real-Time

c. Leverage the Power of 360 Degree View of the Customer.

V. WhatsApp Notifications

a. Manage User Preferences, End-to-End

b. Drive Rich Personalised Conversations

c. Choose from Multiple Templates.

VI. SMS

a. Leverage the Power of Mobile to Stay Connected

b. Personalise your Campaigns, Effortlessly

c. Manage your Existing Contact List, Seamlessly

d. Schedule Campaigns Based on Customers' Time Zones

e. Gain Insights through Real-Time Reporting

f. Conversion Tracking on SMS

VII. Email Marketing

- a. Engage Users through Personalised Broadcasts and Triggered Email Campaigns
- b. Achieve High Email Marketing Open and Click Rates through the Power of AI/ML
- c. Do More with Advanced Customer Segmentation
- d. Breathe Creativity into your Email Campaigns with Customized Templates
- e. Gauge Performance through Intelligent Reports and Interactive Dashboards.

Understand his needs and to understand what exactly does he is willing to communicate about if the communication is of his or her interest they will be interested into it and will look into it.

In addition, we do not have to spend 50 mails per day on him and it is that easy to have the customer's attention just by putting what he actually likes.

This is done to ensure that the funnel leakage is lesser as at the beginning of the funnel he might have too many leads that come into our page but the actual conversion takes a lot over here,

Automation marketing actually comes into play when they will communicate with the customer about the product at that time to buy and.

Communicate with them through push notifications for web notifications when they are not on the website or the app this will help up the seller to actually have the buyer hold onto their product and,

Some or the other time they are willing to convert that that kind of a lead nurturing is very much appreciated in the automation industry and the customer will convert if the offer of the discount that will be placed to him in the end is of his choice.

That way our user will get to understand the product buy it and is more likely to buy more if engaged properly.

There are different firms which offer automation services such as Netcore, Moengage, Webengage, Clevertap, Message 91, Gamooga, Hubspot and so on in India.

All these firms specialize in marketing tools that are helpful to understand the customers and the help them to buy the product and use it integrally by integrating their websites apps and then continue the services.

Now the Big Question arises,

Is it worth paying for such a huge amount on a regular basis?

The solutions mentioned in the following by chosen industries provides evidence of how much more worthy the initial investments can prove to be,

A. For, Ecommerce

The word e-commerce is widely debated and often used to describe various definitions, most often depending on the job role of the person, professional orientation and context, focal product or service, and the type of information technology used (Wigand, 1997).

VIII. Voice

- a. Run Automated Voice Call Campaigns
- b. Automate Personalised Voice Calls at Scale
- c. Establish Instant Conversations with Customers
- d. Track Performance in Real-Time

With all of these features and channels we can understand that the automation marketing industry is flourishing at a good rate the growth rate of this industry is circulated about to be according.

The demand for marketing automation software was estimated at USD 6.08 billion in 2019 and is projected to hit USD 16.87 billion in 2025, at a CAGR of 19.2 per cent over the forecast period (2020 – 2025).

Marketing companies are seeing a rise in their spending, owing to the growing importance of marketing in generating revenue and customer retention we can generally understand that there since so much of investment and prediction is going about there is something that really needs to be taken care of and looked into.

Looking into the competitors for the type of industries that stay that is present currently as the basic idea of an automation industry is to provide its potential client with with good data on which they can help their customers and they can actually communicate, but communicate in the right time, right place and right manner.

The basic propaganda of automation industry automation marketing these days is to ensure that less is more because as time goes, on and on a person who will be receiving 20 mails throughout the day will not looking too much,

As compared to a person who receives only two or three mails at the time when he or she is free or more likely to respond so it is very much advisable to understand the customer.

The e-commerce revolution has fundamentally changed the business of transaction by giving new opportunities and breaking borders easily (Khan, 2016).

Asia-Pacific emerged in 2013 as the world's largest e-Commerce business-to-consumer (B2C) market with revenues of about USD 567.3 billion, a 45 per cent increase over 2012, ahead of Europe (USD 482.3 billion) and North America (USD 452.4 billion) (Price WaterHouse Cooper, 2015).

I. Expedites the purchasing process for new customers.

- a. Boosts the product discovery by analyzing search inputs and providing personalized recommendations.
- b. Customize the on boarding of consumer(s) and push new features or deliver the exploration of new trends with contextual applications.

II. Surging checkouts, while simultaneously receding abandoned/ empty carts

- a. Guide users with specific product suggestions, powered by AI, to exactly what they want-faster.
- b. Custom multichannel cause "reminder-to-complete transaction" campaigns to carry back users exactly where they dropped off.

III. Executing personalized feedbacks to improvise on Cross/ Up selling decisions

- a. Embrace AI's ability to include insightful product recommendations & packages specific to your cart or wish list.
- b. Recommendation & replenishment campaigns cause post purchase via email & device push notifications.

IV. Aggrandizing user retention rate along with accelerating brand loyalty.

- a. Absolutely understand why users keep or uninstall your mobile app when directing them on the ideal conversion route.
- b. Using advanced behavioural analytics & ML models to forecast, arrest and. the user churn with campaigns for re-engagement.

V. Frequently optimising the shopping user experience (UX)

- a. Trigger consumer rating programs or qualitative surveys to gather customer reviews in real time.
- b. Re-engage specific user segments with win back promotions that carry them back to your website or promote re-installation of your app.

Companies like Myntra, Nykaa, fbb and Ckora uses marketing automation in their day-to-day operation in order to achieve desired results along with the aforementioned.

Organisation benefit largely from the use of marketing automation, as digital is replacing traditional means of shopping and there has been a disruption since amazon paved way for online shopping.

Certain testimonials and physical evidence highlighted the following results.

- a. Saw an **uprising 8-13% conversions on website(s)**
- b. A **surge between 6-9% on Add to cart tab**
- c. **Escalation of Marketing ROI up to 10x.**

B. For, Travel and associated industry

The year 2018 has been the 8th year in a row of sustained industry growth, with 1.4 billion international tourism arrivals, according to the UN World Tourism Association. This trend is forecasted to continue through 2020 and beyond. The Asia Pacific neighborhood had the highest inbound industry growth of US\$ 432 billion in 2018; a rise of 7 per cent compared to the previous era. (UNWTO, 2019).

90 per cent of travelers around the world are not happy with the traditional travel process and want a more customized and exclusive approach (Tourwriter, 2019).

Now that online booking is becoming more popular, the user experience is more critical than ever. Apps and websites with robust user experience led to 85 per cent of travelers' booking decisions (Charlton, 2020).

I. A series of constant reminders for new users to proceed them to their first journey

- a. Build a tailored onboard user experience to get them started faster with contextual device walkthroughs.
- b. Make an immediate impression by welcoming new users with customized photos, offers or CTA homepage banners.

II. Compliments to more number of booking completions & reducing the number of Drop-offs

- a. Provide AI-driven recommendations for travel, package or hotel booking based on eyeball data.
- b. Orchestrate multi-channel hyper-personalized promotions to get consumers back to exactly where they dropped off.

III. Makes use of highly personalized recommendation to facilitate the power of cross-sell

- a. Target users who have made a flight reservation with customized hotel choices to increase the average value of your order.
- b. Provision of a multi-channel post-purchase recommendation programs to maximize more sales at the right time.

IV. Boosts CLTV alongside escalation of user retention rate

- a. Understand precisely why users maintain or uninstall their mobile app while directing them on the ideal conversion route.
- b. Using behavioural analytics & ML models to predict, detain, and minimize user uninstallation with re-engagement campaigns in context.

V. Incessant and relentless focus on the customer/ user experience (UX)

- a. Safe real-time reviews through customer rating programs or qualitative surveys on app booking or travel experience.
- b. Raise inactive or churned consumer groups with win back campaigns in order to let them know what they lack.

Online Travel/ e-Travel companies like Make my Trip, Go Ibibo, Ease my trip & Thomas cook (now bankrupt) uses marketing automation to facilitate routine jobs and also to expedite the operations, decreasing down time and allowing minimum intervention in certain activities.

E-travel is a booming industry fuelled by globalisation, whose Key success factors are increasing per capita income complimented by rise in persona disposable income. The trade of people along with other good are on steady rise as inter-country operations is becoming an essential part of the businesses operating across the globe.

Evidence highlighted for this industry backed by data states:

- a. A rise to **12-15% of conversions** through websites
 - b. **Abandoned booking plummeted by 10-12%**
 - c. The **uninstallation rate of app down by 5-10%**.
- C. For Over-the-top/ OTT industry**

The size of the Global Over-the-Top (OTT) Services Market is projected to hit \$179.9 billion by 2025, increasing to 14.3 per cent CAGR market growth over the forecast period (Globenewswire, 2020).

The key factors driving the growth of the demand for OTT services include Internet proliferation with smart device penetration along with simplicity and ease of use to deliver seamless customer experience (Research and Markets, 2020).

The qualitative approach adopted outlined four themes that allow this platform to succeed: simplicity, accessibility, quality, and subscription strategies. These strategic criteria would ensure a higher level of customer engagement for the OTT material (Dasgupta & Grover, 2019).

Between October 2013 and September 2014, India added 43 million internet users (20.5 percent growth) and total internet users reached 254 million 6 in September 2014. Via mobile apps, 235 million, six users accessed the internet. Internet usage growth has been seen in rural as well as urban parts of India.

I. Reminders to new users for first time activation

- a. Show new users how to use your platform effortlessly with contextual program walkthroughs.
- b. Get them started with correct recommendations based on geolocation, type of system and look-alike.

II. Gets existing users to facilitate them on a Binge, pertaining to consumption of content

- a. Offer multi-channel promotions in real time, tailored suggestions & fashion to maximize average time spent per session.
- b. Examines how every user navigates through the platform to find the best conversion route and. pain points for UI / UX.

III. Implements contextual suggestions in order to transcend the Free subscribers (Freemiums) to pre-paid subscribers

- a. Fine-tuning with the content recommendations based on the listening or viewing history of the customers, customer patterns, etc.
- b. It enables to define the North Star Metric and target specific user groups with the appropriate subscription plans.

IV. Amplifying the rate of user retention

- a. Comprehend meticulously why users embrace or uninstall your mobile app whilst observing what keeps them in their habit of using it.
- b. Using sophisticated behavioral analytics & ML models to predict and avoid user attrition with multi-channel strategies for re-engagement.

V. Constant sophistication and improving the platform of User experience (UX)

- a. Trigger consumer rating programs or qualitative one-click surveys to collect input from live customers.
- b. Encourage members who pay to move to new monthly / quarterly / annual plans via well-crafted loyalty programs.

The companies operating in the OTT space are Jio Saavn, Sony LIV, Zee 5, Alt Balaji and Shemaroo has implemented marketing automation to make things easier not only for them but for their customers as well. They study consumer behaviour that enables them to build a highly personalized, tailor made recommendation for each of their user individually.

The trends in this industry enabled by marketing automation is shown below –

- a. An up **rise of 15-20% consumption of content.**
- b. An overall **increase of 25% of Freemium to a paid user.**
- c. A **30% rise in overall DAUs** that are Daily Active users.

The growth hack for the use of marketing automation is to understand the resources where the need is more and where it can be adjusted by other names for example if the daily quota for the daily requirement for the emails is exceeding then how it can be manipulated or taken into consideration and what forward .

3. CONCLUSION

Like all tools, while marketing automation will provide many organizational benefits, it can be quickly abandoned if not used correctly — or worse, it can become a hassle. It is crucial that all companies considering marketing automation comprehend that this is not a simple alternative, which is unable to fix branding and communication design, and that it will have to overcome the difficulties (Wood, 2015).

Nevertheless, the chances of successfully introducing marketing automation are greatly improved by instituting appropriate procedures, correctly scoping needs and goals, and obtaining internal support all with the aid of the right people.

Making investments in technology and people, developing meaningful customer-centered content and being proactive can also help businesses maximize their applied technologies to increase the probability of continued success, and eventually, improve loyalty and income.

REFERENCES

- [1] Charlton, G., 2020. Digital Trends in the Travel Industry: 12 Fascinating Stats: SaleCycle. [Online]
- [2] Available at: <https://www.salecycle.com/blog/stats/digital-trends-travel-industry-12-fascinating-stats/>
- [3] Crazy Egg, 2019. Growth Hacking: The 12 Best Techniques to Boost Conversions: Crazy Egg. [Online]
- [4] Available at: <https://www.crazyegg.com/blog/growth-hacking/>
- [5] Dasgupta, D. S. & Grover, D. P., 2019. UNDERSTANDING ADOPTION FACTORS OF OVER-THE-TOP VIDEO SERVICES AMONG MILLENNIAL CONSUMERS. International Journal of Computer Engineering & Technology (IJCET), pp. 61-71.
- [6] Globenewswire, 2020. Global Over the Top (OTT) Services Market (2019-2025). [Online]
- [7] Available at: <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2020/02/14/1985062/0/en/The-Global-Over-the-Top-OTT-Services-Market-size-is-expected-to-reach-179-9-billion-by-2025-rising-at-a-market-growth-of-14-3-CAGR-during-the-forecast-period.html>
- [8] Heatmap Inc., 2020. Features: Heatmap Inc.. [Online]
- [9] Available at: <https://heatmap.com/#features>
- [10] Khan, A. G., 2016. Electronic Commerce: A Study on Benefits and Challenges in an Emerging Economy. Global Journal of Management and Business Research: Economics and Commerce, pp. 1-5.
- [11] Koyako, 2020. Live Chat Statistics: Koyako. [Online]
- [12] Available at: kayako.com/Kayako_live_chat_stats.pdf

- [13] [Accessed 22 April 2020].
- [14] Patel, S., 2020. How to Leverage Live Chat for Marketing & User Acquisition. [Online]
- [15] Available at:
<https://sujanpatel.com/marketing/growth-hacking-live-chat/>
- [16] Price WaterHouse Cooper, 2015. eCommerce in India Accelerating Growth. [Online]
- [17] Available at:
<https://www.pwc.in/assets/pdfs/publications/2015/e-commerce-in-india-accelerating-growth.pdf>
- [18] Research and Markets, 2020. Global Over-the-Top Services (OTT) Market Outlook, 2020-2024. [Online]
- [19] Available at: <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/global-over-the-top-services-ott-market-outlook-2020-2024---market-set-to-reach-157-billion-by-2024-with-vod-growing-at-the-highest-cagr-300986693.html>
- [20] Smolski, M., 2019. Top 5 Benefits of Email Tracking Software. [Online]
- [21] Available at: <https://blog.mailtag.io/top-5-benefits-of-email-tracking-software/>
- [22] Tourwriter, 2019. Tourism industry statistics for 2019 and beyond: Tourwriter. [Online]
- [23] Available at: <https://www.tourwriter.com/travel-software-blog/2019-tourism-stats/>
- [24] UNWTO, 2019. International Tourism Highlights: UNWTO. [Online]
- [25] Available at:
<https://www.e-unwto.org/doi/pdf/10.18111/9789284421152>
- [26] Wigand, R. T., 1997. Electronic Commerce: Definition, Theory, and Context. Research Gate, pp. 1-16.
- [27] Wood, C. (2015). Marketing automation: Lessons learnt so far.... Journal of Direct, Data and Digital Marketing Practice, 16(4), 251-254